

High-Performance Alumina Fiber and Alumina/Aluminum Composites

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ABSTRACT

Sumitomo Chemical Company has recently developed a process for producing a new type of alumina fiber from polymerized material of organoaluminum compounds. The fiber is in the form of continuous multifilament yarn, featured by excellent mechanical properties and thermal stability, and is most suitable for reinforcement. The alumina fiber/aluminum composites exhibit tensile strengths of 600 to 900MPa and tensile moduli of 110 to 150GPa at 273 to 723°K.

INTRODUCTION

Various types of aluminum oxide fibers have been developed by several companies. Tyco Laboratories has developed a continuous filament of α -alumina of single crystal nature(1). Du Pont has a continuous multifilament yarn of polycrystalline α -alumina designated Fiber FP under development(2). Imperial Chemical Industries has commercialized discontinuous, short fibers of polycrystalline δ -alumina with a trademark of Saffil®(3).

We have recently developed a new type of alumina fiber, a continuous multifilament yarn consisting of ultrafine crystallites of spinel structure. The fiber is suited for reinforcing resins, ceramics, and, especially, light metals, because it has a well-balanced combination of high strength and modulus and, consequently, good handleability, stability at high temperatures, excellent compatibility with resins and metals, and high electrical resistivity. This paper reports the fabrication process and properties of the fiber and the alumina/aluminum composites.

SUMITOMO'S ALUMINA FIBER

Process

The schematic of the process for producing our alumina fiber is shown in Figure 1. It is a novel process suitable for producing a continuous, high-strength fiber on an industrial scale. First an organoaluminum compound such as trialkyl aluminum or trialkoxy aluminum is polymerized by adding a controlled amount of water. The resultant polymer, polyaluminumoxane, is dissolved in an organic solvent together with a silicon-containing compound such as alkyl silicate to prepare a viscous spinning mix. The precursor fibers are produced

Figure 1 Process for producing Sumitomo's Alumina Fiber

Figure 2 Sumitomo's Alumina Yarn

from the mix by a dry-spinning method which is commonly used for industrial production of some organic fibers. Finally the precursor fibers are fired in air to a temperature higher than 1,000°K.

The organic pendant groups of polyaluminumoxane and silicon-containing compounds are thermally decomposed and removed in the temperature range below 1,000°K at which temperature the fibers are purely inorganic, consisting of Al_2O_3 and SiO_2 . The chemical composition of the fiber is adjusted by changing the amount of the silicon-containing compounds added to the spinning mix so that the properties of the alumina fiber are optimized in each of specific applications. The fiber of the standard grade are made to contain 15 wt% of SiO_2 . A typical bobbin of our continuous alumina yarn is shown in Figure 2.

Structure

The fiber which is fired up to 1,000°K consists of only Al_2O_3 and SiO_2 of high purity. The structure at this stage is amorphous as observed by X-ray² diffraction shown in Figure 3. As the fiber is fired to a still higher temperature, it undergoes a transition at around 1,240°K, at which temperature a sharp exothermic peak is observed in the differential thermal analysis and the structure changes from the amorphous structure to spinel, or γ - or η -alumina type structure, as observed by X-ray diffraction shown also in Figure 3.

The fibers used for reinforcement are produced by firing them at a temperature higher than 1,250°K so that they consist of fine crystallites of spinel. An electron microscope operating at 1,000kV showed that the size of the crystallites is of several nanometers. The scanning electron micrographs of the fiber are shown in Figure 4. The filaments are dense and look like glass indicating

that they are composed of extremely fine crystallites.

The role of added SiO_2 is to stabilize the spinel structure and to prevent the fiber from transforming to α -alumina which tends to grow in crystal size and thus becoming brittle. In fact, even after the fiber is heated for 100 hours at $1,400^\circ\text{K}$, no other crystal forms than the spinel are detected by X-ray diffraction.

Properties

Some major properties of our alumina fiber are summarized in Table 1. Special features of the fiber are:

- (1) It is continuous.
- (2) It has high tensile strengths of 1.8 to 2.6GPa and
- (3) high moduli of 210 to 250GPa, which are comparable to graphite fibers.
- (4) It exhibits good adhesion to resins because the fiber has spinel structure, but not α -alumina structure, and the fiber surface is moderately active.
- (5) It is colorless and transparent, and
- (6) electrically insulating.
- (7) It is stable at high temperatures in air because it is made of alumina

Figure 3 X-ray diffraction of Alumina Fiber

Figure 4 Scanning electron micrographs of Alumina Fiber

and silica.

- (8) It is not deteriorated by molten metals.
- (9) It is chemically resistant.

Our process is most suitable for producing a high-performance alumina fiber for several reasons. First, since the spinning mix is a viscous solution of polymeric material, polyaluminumoxane, in an organic solvent and has excellent spinnability, it is easy to produce continuous multifilament precursor yarns from the mix, which may then be converted by firing to continuous alumina yarns suitable for reinforcing various materials. Secondly, since the starting material is a kind of organoaluminum compound, it undergoes a unique structural change during firing, the situation being essentially different from firing of ordinary aluminum hydroxides, and finally transforms into extremely fine crystallite. The fiber is consequently dense and has high strength and high modulus.

ALUMINA/EPOXY COMPOSITES

Properties

Table 2 lists some properties of epoxy resin reinforced by the present alumina fiber. The FRP is featured by :

- (1) high tensile strength, with flexural strength of 1.56GPa,
- (2) high modulus, with flexural modulus of 122GPa,
- (3) excellent compressive strength of over 1.4GPa,

Table 1 Properties of Sumitomo's Alumina Fiber

Chemical composition		
Al ₂ O ₃	(wt%)	85
SiO ₂	(wt%)	15
Crystal phase		Spinel
Fundamental physical properties		
Density	(Mg/m ³)	3.2
Specific surface area	(m ² /kg)	<1000
Filament characteristics		
Diameter	(μm)	17 (9* ¹)
Filament length	(m)	continuous (0.1* ¹)
Filaments/yarn		380
Mechanical properties		
Tensile strength	(GPa)	1.8 (2.6* ¹)
Tensile modulus	(GPa)	210 (250* ¹)
Vickers hardness		1,810 - 1,930
Thermal properties		
Max. use temperature * ²	(K)	1,523
Coef. of thermal expansion	(1/K)	8.8 x 10 ⁻⁶ (at 473-773 K)
Specific heat	(kJ/kg.K)	0.71 (at 302K) / 1.00 (at 673K)
Optical properties		
Appearance		colorless and transparent
Refractivity index (n _D ²⁰)		1.65
Chemical resistance * ³		
6N HCl	(%)	<5
18N H ₂ SO ₄	(%)	<5
7N HNO ₃	(%)	<5
30% NaOH aq.	(%)	10

*¹For fibers made on a laboratory scale

*²Temperature at which tensile strength (directly measured at the temperature) falls down by 10% of tensile strength measured at room temperature

*³Weight loss after immersion for 6 hrs at 353K

- (4) electrically insulating,
 (5) low attenuation of electromagnetic wave of 10^6 to 10^{10} Hz, and
 (6) being colorless.

Materials which possess the combination of the above properties, especially, light weight, high modulus and electrically insulating at the same time, have hardly been available previously.

Table 2 Properties of Unidirectional FRP

Density	(Mg/m ³)	2.4
Tensile strength (0°)* ¹	(GPa)	1.35(1.7)* ²
(90°)	(GPa)	0.068
Tensile modulus (0°)	(GPa)	137
(90°)	(GPa)	18
Flexural strength (0°)	(GPa)	1.56(1.8)* ²
Flexural modulus (0°)	(GPa)	122
Flexural fatigue strength at 10 ⁷ cycles (0°)	(GPa)	0.63
Compressive strength (0°)	(GPa)	1.4
Interlaminar shear strength	(GPa)	0.13
Izod impact (0°)	(J/cm ²)	20
Rockwell hardness		E85
Thermal expansion (0°)	(1/K)	0.4×10^{-5}
(90°)	(1/K)	3.7×10^{-5}
Thermal conductivity (0°)	(W/m.K)	2.32
(90°)	(W/m.K)	0.85
Volume electrical resistivity(90°)	(Ω .m)	10^{13}
Surface electrical resistivity	(Ω)	$10^{14} - 10^{16}$
Arc resistance time	(s)	130 - 180
Dielectric strength	(KV/mm)	16 - 20
Dielectric constant at 10 ⁶ Hz		4.5
at 10 ¹⁰ Hz		4.2
Tangent loss at 10 ⁶ Hz		0.012
at 10 ¹⁰ Hz		0.015

Fiber content : 60 vol%, unidirectional

Resin : DDM type epoxy resin (Sumitomo's SUMIEPOXY[®] ELM-434)

Hardner : DDS

*¹0° and 90° in the parentheses indicate the angle between fiber direction and load direction.

*²For FRP made from laboratory scale fibers.

ALUMINA/ALUMINUM COMPOSITES

Fabrication

In order to fabricate alumina/aluminum composites, we tried to develop a method in which the reinforcing fibers are incorporated into molten aluminum, that is, casting method, by making use of one of the main features of the alumina fiber that it is resistant to molten aluminum, whereas other fibers such as graphite fibers and boron fibers are damaged by molten aluminum. The method has several advantages. First, it is easy to fabricate composites having complicated forms compared with other methods such as diffusion bonding or hot-pressing of prepregs(4). Secondly, good adhesion between fibers and matrix aluminum is achieved because molten metals are generally reactive.

The alumina fiber is not wetted by molten aluminum and pressure must be applied in order for the metal to infiltrate into the fiber bundles. We have developed two methods. In one method, which is shown in Figure 5 and is used

mainly for laboratory scale fabrication, a combination of vacuum and inert gas pressure is used: a fiber bundle is put into a carbon mould, one end of the mould is immersed in molten aluminum kept in a crucible, vacuum and then inert gas pressure of 0.5 to 5MPa is applied, and finally the whole system is cooled and the composite is taken out of the mould and machined.

Another method, which is applicable to industrial production, follows an ordinary squeeze casting method: a pre-form is first made of fibers and an organic binder, the pre-form is loaded into a mould, the binder is burnt off, molten aluminum is poured into the mould, and mechanically pressed by plunger action. Some composites made by the squeeze casting method are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 5 Liquid metal infiltration apparatus using inert gas pressure

Figure 6 Alumina/aluminum composites fabricated by squeeze casting method

Although the alumina fiber is not wetted by molten aluminum, it was found that, when once the fiber is made into contact with molten aluminum by applying pressure, good adhesion is achieved between the fiber and the metal as shown in the scanning electron micrographs of the fracture surface of the composite shown in Figure 7.

Properties

Evaluation of the properties of alumina/aluminum composites was carried out on the test pieces made with the alumina fiber and aluminum or aluminum-copper binary alloy having a Cu content of 5 wt%. The tensile, flexural, and compressive properties were measured for 0°, 45°, and 90° directions of unidirectional composites and for 0° direction of ±45° plies composites in the temperature range from 293 to 823°K. Tests were conducted on a 500 kilogram or a 25 ton Shimazu Autograph with a cross-head speed of 1mm/min, using coupons of 10 mm wide, 5 mm thick, and 100 mm long for measurement of tensile properties, 20 mm wide, 2 mm

Fractured at 293°K

Fractured at 723°K

Figure 7 SEM photographs of fracture surface of Alumina/aluminum composite

thick, and 70 mm long for flexural properties, and 9x9 mm and 20 mm long for compressive properties.

The results are summarized in Table 3 together with other physical properties. The tensile and flexural properties are plotted against temperature in Figure 8. The composites are featured by:

- (1) low specific gravity, less than half of that of steel,
- (2) high strength at high temperatures, with tensile strength of 670 to 860 MPa at 723°K, and
- (3) high modulus at high temperatures, with tensile modulus of over 100GPa at 723°K.

The alumina/aluminum composites have another feature that, since the alumina fiber is electrically non-conductive, no galvanic corrosion is induced.

Figure 8 Tensile and flexural properties vs temperature

Table 3 Properties of Alumina/Aluminum Composites

		Alumina/Al	Alumina/Al+5%Cu
Density	(Mg/m ³)	2.9	2.9
Tensile strength	(0°)* ¹ at 293°K (MPa)	860	590
	(45°)		280
	(90°)		230
	(0°) at 723°K	860	670
Tensile modulus	(0°) at 293°K (GPa)	150	150
	(90°)		50
	(0°) at 723°K		110
Tensile fatigue strength			
at 10 ⁷ cycles	(0°) at 298°K (MPa)	400* ²	250
	(90°)		80
Flexural strength	(0°) at 293°K (MPa)	1,100	1,000
	(45°)		800
	(0°) at 723°K	800	950
Flexural modulus	(0°) at 293°K (GPa)	135	135
	(0°) at 723°K		100
Flexural fatigue strength			
at 10 ⁷ cycles	(0°) at 298°K (MPa)	300* ²	
Compressive strength	(0°) at 293°K (MPa)		2,200
	(45°)		580
	(90°)		400
	(0°) at 723°K		580
Compressive modulus	(0°) at 293°K (GPa)		140
Charpy impact	(0°) at 293°K (J/cm ²)	9.4	2.2
	(45°)		3.0
	(90°)		2.0
	(0°) at 723°K		3.0
Stress for minimum creep rate			
of 0.0001%/hr	(0°) at 623-723°K (MPa)		260
Specific heat	(kJ/kg.K)	0.88	
Thermal expansion	(0°) (1/K)	7.6x10 ⁻⁶	* ²
	(90°)	14.0x10 ⁻⁶	* ²
Thermal conductivity	(90°) (W/m.K)	34.8	

Fiber content : 50 vol%, unidirectional

*¹0°, 45°, and 90° in the parentheses indicate the angle between fiber direction and load direction.*²According to T. Furuta of National Aerospace Laboratory, Japan.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Some attractive properties of the alumina fiber and the composites have been demonstrated. Applications of these new materials are being considered for various items and areas such as radar transparent structures, electrical equipments, engine parts, and structure members of aircrafts. Research programs are also in progress in order to further improve the tensile strength of the fiber from current 1.8GPa to over 2.5GPa on a large scale production.

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